

Effects Of Zinc Oxide Nano-Particles And Farm Manure On Wheat Yield Grown On Salt Affected Soil Conditions

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ABSTRACT

Soils contaminated with salt are known to cause land degradation and large abiotic stress to crops. The study attempted to look at the effect of using farm manure (FM) and zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO-NPs) on the yield of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) in salty soil. The experiment was conducted in the Faisalabad (UAF) Institute of Soil and Environmental Sciences (ISES) warehouse. The number of replications was three with a completely randomized design (CRD) and nine treatments i.e., T0 (control without any application), T1 (ZnO-NP 25%), T2 (ZnO NP 25% + 25g FM/pot), T3 (ZnO-NP 50%), T4 (ZnO-NP 50% + 25g FM/pot), T5 (ZnO NP 75%),

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T6 (ZnO-NP 75% + 2 Growth, physiological properties and yield of wheat and post-harvest soil analysis were carried out. Following the experiment, findings showed that FM and Zn-NPs application were significantly better in enhancing growth attributes. A 100% ZnO-NP concentration containing 25gm FM (T8) resulted in the highest amount of chlorophyll content and number of tillers i.e. 40 and 6.5 percentage increase over control respectively. T6 and T8 were optimal in the number of spikes (47% increase) and total biomass production in plants (45% increase), respectively. It was also determined that Zn-NPs used together with FM led to improved crop growth, yield and physiology besides improving the soil health of salt-affected soil. These amendments could, therefore, be suggested as a sustainable measure to boost the production of wheat in salt-contaminated soils to ensure sustainable production of the food crop.

Keywords: Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles; Farm Manure; Saline-Sodic Soil; Wheat Productivity; Soil Health; Sustainable Agriculture

Introduction

In today's world, where the world has become globalized, there are major challenges for sustainable food crop production because of soil deterioration due to soil degradation and salt accumulation in soil (Abbas et al., 2023). Soil salinity has become a critical issue where the number of soluble salts plays a substantial role in the degradation of fertile soils, at an alarming rate of 1-2% loss every year (Hossain et al., 2019). Globally an estimated 831-932 million hectares of land are affected by different forms of soil salinity such as saline, sodic, and saline-sodic soils (Osman, 2018). These soils are distributed at 23% saline, 37% sodic and 40% saline-sodic (Solomon et al., 2023). Pakistan alone has around 6.7 Mha salt affected land out of which 2.67 Mha is in Punjab (Qureshi and Perry, 2021). Salt-affected soils not only impair the quality of land, but also impose major abiotic stress on crops. The main problems encountered in these soils are their salinity and their deterioration in structure, leading to low crops productivity (Chaganti et al., 2015).

Anthropogenic factors like use of brackish ground water and lack of high-quality irrigation water are major contributors of soil salinity (Bukhari et al., 2021). Additional factors, such as imbalanced application of fertilizers, low soil organic matter (SOM), high soil pH and arid to semi-arid climatic conditions increase the problem by boosting evapotranspiration and salt accumulation on the soil surface (Khalid et al., 2013). High salinity has a negative impact on plants by ion toxicity, osmotic stress, and nutritional imbalances, which lead to reduced root efficiency in water uptake (Fu and Yung, 2023). Increased sodium (Na⁺) levels affect nutrient uptake and limit growth and nutrient content of cereal crops such as wheat (Rahnama et al., 2011). Under salt stress, reactive oxygen species (ROS) are produced in plants, which disrupts photosynthesis, hormone regulation, and antioxidant defense mechanisms (Yaseen et al., 2021). Excessive amount of sodium in the soil also leads to the dispersion of soil aggregates, degradation of soil structure and low fertility (Ellouzi et al., 2023). These soluble salts usually contain chlorides, carbonates, and bicarbonates of sodium (Na), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg) and potassium (K) (Ali, 2011).

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Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is one of the most widely cultivated cereal crops in the world and is used as a staple food, especially in developing countries (Adil et al., 2022). Its demand is still increasing because of population increases even though it is being partly replaced by other cereals to achieve food security (Chand and Jumrani, 2009). Globally, wheat production is projected to be challenged because of increasing consumption (FAO, 2018). In Pakistan, wheat is grown on 22 million acres and it accounts for 1.8% of the national GDP and 7.8% of the agricultural sector. Recent reports suggest a decline in production (27.53 to 26.42 million tons). Low yield in wheat is mainly caused by salinity and insufficient application of fertilizer (Shahzad et al., 2019), as wheat is moderately salt-tolerant (Wang et al., 2020).

Micronutrients are very important for the survival, growth and completion of the life cycle of crops. Zinc (Zn) is an essential micronutrient that is responsible for the activation of more than 300 enzymes that are involved in key processes, such as DNA synthesis, protein production, and cell division (Mazhar et al., 2023). Zn deficiency decreases crop yield, decreases physiological functions, and adversely impacts the production of nodules, nitrogen fixation, and hemoglobin synthesis (Raj and Raj, 2019). In alkaline soils, Zn availability falls very rapidly, reducing 30-fold when pH is greater than 8 (Sadeghzadeh et al., 2013). Environmental factors like photolysis, leaching, and microbial degradation contribute to the further limitation of Zn bioavailability, which lessens the effectiveness of applied fertilizers (Qaswar et al., 2017).

Deficiency of Zn is present in plants as well as humans. In crops it causes stunted growth, disease susceptibility and low yield while in humans, it leads to impaired immunity, delayed growth and reproductive issues, and increased susceptibility to diseases (Cakmak and Kutman, 2018). To overcome the problem of Zn deficiency, several approaches have been devised such as soil and foliar application of Zn fertilizers, seed priming, fertigation and root dipping in Zn solutions (Cakmak, 2008). Among these, zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO-NPs) have become an efficient method, because of its small size, high surface area and unique physicochemical properties, which enhances Zn uptake and translocation more effectively than conventional fertilizers (Zeng et al., 2020). Studies have shown that ZnO-NPs have improved germination, root biomass, plant growth and yield in crops such as chickpea, mung bean, and cotton and reduce oxidative stress and increase salt tolerance (Mahajan et al., 2011).

Organic manures, in the form of farm manure (FM), are commonly used for enhancing soil health, especially in salt affected soils. FM improves the soil aggregation, SOM content, and nutrient availability and reduces the phytotoxicity of ZnO-NPs (Usman et al., 2020). Increased humic acid (HA) from FM balances the charges of ZnO-NPs, soil aggregates and enhances the overall soil physicochemical properties (El-Sharkawy et al., 2021). The aim of the study is to assess the influence of ZnO-NPs on Zn concentration in wheat grains and assess the combined influence of ZnO-NPs and FM on the growth and soil health of wheat under salt affected conditions to promote sustainable agriculture practices.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Site

The experiment was conducted to evaluate the effects of zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO-NPs) and farmyard manure (FM) on wheat yield in salt-affected soil. The study was carried out in the wire house of the Institute of Soil and Environmental Sciences (ISES), University of Agriculture Faisalabad, Pakistan.

Soil Collection and Preparation

Saline-sodic soil was collected from Chak No. 62/RB, Tehsil Jaranwala, District Faisalabad. The soil was air-dried, sieved through a 2 mm sieve, and pre-analyzed for pH, electrical conductivity (ECe), sodium (Na^+), calcium and magnesium ($\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+}$), carbonates (CO_3^{2-}), bicarbonates (HCO_3^-), chloride (Cl^-), sodium adsorption ratio (SAR), zinc content, and soil texture (Bouyoucos, 1962; US Salinity Laboratory Staff, 1954). Soil texture was classified using the International Textural Triangle.

Table 2.1. Physico-Chemical Characteristics of Experimental Soil

Parameter	Unit	Value
ECe	dS m ⁻¹	13.77
pHs	-	8.68
CO_3^{2-}	mmolc L ⁻¹	Nil
HCO_3^-	mmolc L ⁻¹	8
Cl^-	mmolc L ⁻¹	31
$\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+}$	mmolc L ⁻¹	11
Saturation Percentage	%	21.4
Texture	-	Clay loam
Organic Matter	%	0.517
Zinc	mg kg ⁻¹	0.09

Treatment Layout

Nine treatments were applied with varying levels of ZnO-NPs and FM:

Treatment	Description	Treatment	Description
T0	Control (no ZnO-NPs)	T1	25% ZnO-NPs
T2	25% ZnO-NPs + 25 g FM	T3	50% ZnO-NPs
T4	50% ZnO-NPs + 25 g FM	T5	75% ZnO-NPs
T6	75% ZnO-NPs + 25 g FM	T7	100% ZnO-NPs
T8	100% ZnO-NPs + 25 g FM		

Each pot contained 5 kg of soil. Recommended doses of nitrogen (46 kg ha⁻¹), phosphorus (25 kg ha⁻¹) and potassium (64 kg ha⁻¹) were used in urea, diammonium phosphate (DAP) and sulphate of potash (SOP), respectively. Six to eight wheat seeds (cv. Dilkash) were sown to a pot and seedlings were reduced to

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five. Amendments and irrigation were made to it through organic means and treatments.

Growth Parameters

Measured growth parameters included: Plant height, spike length, number of spikes and tillers, fresh and dry shoot weight and 100 grain weight and Gaseous exchange parameters (photosynthesis, transpiration, respiration) were recorded using infrared gas analyzer (IRGA).

Plant and Grain

Analysis Shoot and grain samples were powdered. The amount of zinc was established through tri-acid digestion (HNO_3 - H_2SO_4 - HClO_4) and atomic absorption spectrophotometry on the filtered and diluted solution (50 mL).

Workflow Soil and Plant Analysis

The flowchart 2.1 shows the experimental procedure of the wheat pot experiment. It starts with the collection of soil, drying, sieving and pre-analysis, followed by preparation of soil and treatment application. Wheat is then sown and irrigated and monitored for growth, with measurements being taken before the wheat is harvested. Lastly, the analyses of soil and vegetation samples are performed on the chemical properties and zinc level by means of common laboratory methods.

Flowchart 2.1. Experimental Procedure and Analyses

RESULTS

Physiological attributes

Photosynthetic rate

As per Figure. 3.1, ZnO-NP and FM demonstrated a notably significant impact on photosynthetic rate. The T₈ (ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM pot⁻¹) had significant (P = 0.0000) effects on the photosynthetic rate in wheat when subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA). The application of ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM pot⁻¹ (T₈) had a 40% of the photosynthetic rate due to the combined application of ZnO-NPs and FM when compared to control. The photosynthetic rate was also significantly higher in treatments, T₂, T₃, T₄, T₆, T₇, and T₈ than in control by 22%, 25%, 21%, 24%, 35%, 30%, and 40%, respectively.

Fig.3.1: Effect of treatments on photosynthetic rate of wheat. Control: without any application, T₁: ZnO-NP 25%, T₂: ZnO-NP 25% and 25gm FM, T₃: ZnO-NP 50%, T₄: ZnO-NP 50% and 25gm FM, T₅: ZnO-NP 75%, T₆: ZnO-NP 75% and 25gm FM, and T₇: ZnO-NP 100%, T₈: ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM.

Transpiration rate

As showed in figure 3.2 exhibits the positive impact of FM and ZnO-NP on transpiration rate at different concentrations. Wheat transpiration rate is significantly affected (P = 0.0073) by ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm. according to the analysis of variance (ANOVA). The highest transpiration rate was obtained in T₈ with application of ZnO-NP 100% + 25gm FM). 14% increase in T₈ as compared to control. In control treatment no application of FM and ZnO NPs therefore, it was severely affected due to salt stress and other abiotic factors that reduced transpiration rate owing to ionic imbalance. Moreover, in comparison to the control, the transpiration rate increased significantly by 7%, 7%, 8%, 9%, 10%, 12%, 11%, and 13% in treatments T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄, T₅, T₆, T₇, and T₈ respectively. These data showed that increased in transpiration rate in wheat crops under salt-effect soil has a significant impact on both organic matter and Zn which reduced salt stress in cop.

Figure 3.2: Effect of treatments on the transpiration rate of wheat. Control: without any application, T1: ZnO-NP 25%, T2: ZnO-NP 25% and 25gm FM, T3: ZnO-NP 50%, T4: ZnO-NP 50% and 25gm FM, T5: ZnO-NP 75%, T6: ZnO-NP 75% and 25gm FM, and T7: ZnO-NP 100%, T8: ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM.

Chlorophyll content

Figure 3.3 Shows the positive effect of ZnO-NP and FM on chlorophyll content in wheat plant grown and salt stress condition. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) shows the significant ($P = 0.0000$) effect of ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM on the chlorophyll content of wheat in T₈ treatment. Maximum chlorophyll content was recorded in T₈. Chlorophyll content minimum in control treatment due to abiotic factors which have great impact on wheat crop. In treatments such as T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄, T₅, T₆, T₇, T₈ chlorophyll content was also significantly increased by 10%, 11%, 9%, 12%, 9%, 13%, 14% and 16% as compared to control, respectively.

Figure 3.3: Effect of treatments on chlorophyll content of wheat. Control: without any application, T1: ZnO-NP 25%, T2: ZnO-NP 25% and 25gm FM, T3: ZnO-NP 50%, T4: ZnO-NP 50% and 25gm FM, T5: ZnO-NP 75%, T6: ZnO-NP 75% and 25gm FM, and T7: ZnO-NP 100%, T8: ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM.

Zinc content in wheat grain

Figure 3.4 shows the positive effect of ZnO-NP and FM on Zn content in wheat plant grown salt stress conditions. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) shows the significant ($P = 0.0000$) effect of ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM on Zn content of wheat in T8 treatment. Maximum chlorophyll content was recorded in T8. Zn content minimum in control treatment due to abiotic factors which have great impact on wheat crop. Especially in salt effected soil Zn concentration is lesser than normal soils.

Agronomic parameters

Plant height

Figure 3.4: Effect of treatments on Zinc content in wheat grain. Control: without any application, T1: ZnO-NP 25%, T2: ZnO-NP 25% and 25gm FM, T3: ZnO-NP 50%, T4: ZnO-NP 50% and 25gm FM, T5: ZnO-NP 75%, T6: ZnO-NP 75% and 25gm FM, and T7: ZnO-NP 100%, T8: ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM.

Figure 3.5 shows the positive effect of both FM and Zn-NPs amendments on wheat plant height under salinity stress soil. Analysis of variance (Table 4.4) shows the significant ($P = 0.0000$) effect of T_0 which was control had lower plant height as compared to T_8 . In T_8 treatments ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM have a greater effect on plant height of wheat. Maximum plant height was recorded in T_8 over to the control treatment and as well as other treatments. Increase of 49.3% is observed with T_8 as compared to control. In treatments T_1 , T_2 , T_3 , T_4 , T_5 , T_6 , T_7 , and T_8 plant heights were also significantly increased by 46.3%, 46.7%, 46.3%, 46.8%, 46.5%, 47.6%, 47.4%, and 49.3% as compared to control, respectively.

Figure 3.5: Effect of treatments on plant height of wheat. Control: without any application, T1: ZnO-NP 25%, T2: ZnO-NP 25% and 25gm FM, T3: ZnO-NP 50%, T4: ZnO-NP 50% and 25gm FM, T5: ZnO-NP 75%, T6: ZnO-NP 75% and 25gm FM, and T7: ZnO-NP 100%, T8: ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM.

Number of tillers/ plants

Figure 3.6 indicated the positive impact of ZnO-NP and FM application on the number of tillers in wheat plants. The analysis of variance (table 4.5) revealed a significant ($P=0.0009$) effect of treatment which was ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM on the number of tillers of wheat, with the maximum number of tillers recorded in T₀ treatment. Specifically, an increase of 8% was observed in the number of tillers with T₈ compared to the control. Additionally, treatments T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄, T₅, T₆, T₇, and T₈ also showed significant increases in the number of tillers by 4%, 5%, 4%, 6%, 5%, 6%, and 8%, respectively, over to the control.

Number of spikes

Figure 3.7 indicates that the positive of ZnO-NP and FM amendments on the number of spikes in wheat plants is demonstrated. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) (table

Figure 3.6: Effect of treatments on number of tillers of wheat. Control: without any application, T₁: ZnO-NP 25%, T₂: ZnO-NP 25% and 25gm FM, T₃: ZnO-NP 50%, T₄: ZnO-NP 50% and 25gm FM, T₅: ZnO-NP 75%, T₆: ZnO-NP 75% and 25gm FM, and T₇: ZnO-NP 100%, T₈: ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM.

Figure 3.7: Effect of treatments on number of spikes of wheat. Control: without any application, T₁: ZnO-NP 25%, T₂: ZnO-NP 25% and 25gm FM, T₃: ZnO-NP 50%, T₄: ZnO-NP 50% and 25gm FM, T₅: ZnO-NP 75%, T₆: ZnO-NP 75% and 25gm FM, and T₇: ZnO-NP 100%, T₈: ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM.

4.6) reveals a significant ($P=0.000$) effect of these amendments on the number of spikes, with the highest number recorded in treatment T₈ when ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM used as compared to the control treatment. It also indicates that a significant increases number of spikes were observed in T₆ and T₈ by 38% and 40%, respectively. Additionally, treatments T₁, showed significant increases of 10%, 15%

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17%, 25%, 27% 38% 35% 40% according to treatments T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄, T₅, T₆, T₇, and T₈ respectively, in contrast to the T₀.

Plant total weight

Figure 3.8 showed that the positive effect of ZnO-NP and FM amendments extends to plant total weight in wheat. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) reveals a positive significant ($P= 0.000$) effect of these amendments on the plant total weight, with the highest total weight recorded in treatment T₈ with concentration of ZnO-NP was 100% and 25gm FM. Specifically, an increase of 45% was observed in the plant total weight with T₈ compared to the control. Additionally, treatments T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄, T₅, T₆, T₇, and T₈ also showed significant increases in plant total weight by 21%, 24%, 23%, 25%, 24%, 32%, 29% and 45%, respectively, in comparison with the control.

Figure 3.8: Effect of treatments on plant total weight of wheat. Control: without any application, T₁: ZnO-NP 25%, T₂: ZnO-NP 25% and 25gm FM, T₃: ZnO-NP 50%, T₄: ZnO-NP 50% and 25gm FM, T₅: ZnO-NP 75%, T₆: ZnO-NP 75% and 25gm FM, and T₇: ZnO-NP 100%, T₈: ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM. In addition, it increased of 29% T₈ as compared to control. There is also significant effect on T₆ as well with compared to T₀.

Figure 3.9: Effect of treatments on spike length of wheat. Control: without any application, T1: ZnO-NP 25%, T2: ZnO-NP 25% and 25gm FM, T3: ZnO-NP 50%, T4: ZnO-NP 50% and 25gm FM, T5: ZnO-NP 75%, T6: ZnO-NP 75% and 25gm FM, and T7: ZnO-NP 100%, T8: ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM.

Soil parameters

Soil organic carbon

Figure 3.10 shows the positive effect of ZnO-NPs and FM applications on soil organic carbon. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) shows the significant ($P = 0.0000$) effect of ZnO-NPs and 25gm FM on wheat. Maximum soil organic carbon was recorded in T₂, T₄, T₆, and T₈. Increase in SOC was observed in T₈ as compared to control. Increase in SOC due to the farm manure which was used to enhance the soil carbon and soil nutrient concentration. In addition, it lowers organic content in other treatments. Therefore, applying FM has significant effects on soil health and improve plant growth.

Figure 3.10: Effect of treatments on soil organic matter. Control: without any application, T1: ZnO-NP 25%, T2: ZnO-NP 25% and 25gm FM, T3: ZnO-NP 50%, T4: ZnO-NP 50% and 25gm FM, T5: ZnO-NP 75%, T6: ZnO-NP 75% and 25gm FM, and T7: ZnO-NP 100%, T8: ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM.

Soil EC_e

Figure 3.11 shows Soil EC_e is one of the most crucial factors in checking reclamation of salt affected soils. It indicated that positive effect of ZnO-NPs and FM applications on EC_e in soil. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) shows the significant ($P = 0.0000$) effect of ZnO-NPs and FM on EC_e of soil. Maximum decrease in soil EC_e was recorded in T₈ (ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM). Decrease of 25% is observed in T₈ as compared to the control. Decrease in EC_e of soil is due to antagonistic effect of organic. Owing to OM has significant effect on EC_e due to change chemical composition of soil. Moreover, Zn nano particles have also potential to lower the EC_e of soil.

Figure 3.11: Effect of treatments on post-wheat harvest soil ECe. Control: without any application, T1: ZnO-NP 25%, T2: ZnO-NP 25% and 25gm FM, T3: ZnO-NP 50%, T4: ZnO-NP 50% and 25gm FM, T5: ZnO-NP 75%, T6: ZnO-NP 75% and 25gm FM, and T7: ZnO-NP 100%, T8: ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM.

Soil pH_s

Figure 3.12 shows the positive effect of ZnO-NPs and FM applications on pH_s in soil. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) shows the significant ($P = 0.0000$) effect of ZnO-NPs and FM on pH_s of wheat. Minimum pH_s in soil was recorded in T₈ (ZnO-NP100% and 25gm FM). The maximum pH_s is observed in control as compared to amendment treatments. So, these results revealed that FM and Zn have greater impact on soil pH_s.

Figure 3.12: Effect of treatments on post-wheat harvest soil pH_s. Control: without any application, T1: ZnO-NP 25%, T2: ZnO-NP 25% and 25gm FM, T3: ZnO-NP 50%, T4: ZnO-NP 50% and 25gm FM, T5: ZnO-NP 75%, T6: ZnO-NP 75% and 25gm FM, and T7: ZnO-NP 100%, T8: ZnO-NP 100% and 25gm FM.

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DISCUSSION

According to our results, adding FM to saline-sodic soils decreased the Sodium Adsorption Ratio (SAR) compared to control conditions (El-Shazely et al. 2021). In addition, FM dramatically decreased Na^+ and SAR and increased K and Ca+Mg compared to control treatment. Rehana et al. (2008) reported the wheat yield was increased and enhanced waterholding capacity with the application of FYM and over the control. The findings of application of FYM improved concentration in different depths of soils. (Ding et al. 2021) reported Vermicompost application reduces the value of EC and SAR in saline-sodic. (Sinha and Herat, 2012) concluded that FM increases pore spaces, water holding capacity, and high aeration drainage as compared to control.

Indicator for human nutrition, the rising concentration of macronutrients, particularly nitrogen (N), in grains is a sign of wheat quality. Findings indicated that lowering the moisture level significantly reduced the amount of N, P, and K (Awasthi et al. 2014), due to low uptake of nutrients because of salinity which induced biotic stress in wheat plants. the application of ZnO-NPs and FM significantly increased the N and K content across all moisture levels. However, P showed only a slight increase in concentration across all treatments. The decrease in P concentration is primarily attributed to the antagonistic effect of Zn on phosphorus uptake (Rietra et al. 2017). Zn concentration increased in 100% of ZnO-NPs and with recommended FM as compared to lower concentration of ZnO-NPs and as well in control which was observed least in contents of Zn in this experiment.

The phenomena could be explained by Zinc's crucial function in augmenting protein synthesis, preserving membrane integrity, encouraging cellular elongation, and invigorating active nutrient uptake by plant roots. Together, these processes help plants absorb nutrients more efficiently (Ahmed et al. 2021). Moreover, grains exhibited higher concentrations of macronutrients compared to straw. The wheat grain under conditions of less than 100 ppm ZnO-NPs and 25 gm of FM showed the highest values of N, P, and K at 1.92, 0.42, and 1.65, respectively, in comparison to the control. ZnO-NPs improve the overall nutritional value of wheat plants and help with plant growth and physiological factors including photosynthetic and respiration rates. Consequently, they help mitigate the adverse effects of drought (Abd El-Aziz et al. 2022). Owing to FM is the source of nutrients and stabilized soil aggregates which were deteriorated by salt-affected. It overcomes these problems and enhances plants' health and as well soil conditions.

Wheat production has ultimately increased in tandem with the plant's general growth and uptake of macronutrients. Wheat treated with varying concentrations of ZnONPs exhibits notable differences from the control. These results correspond with research that under water stress, maize yield was enhanced by nano zinc at a dose of 100 mg L^{-1} (Sun et al. (2020). While the lack of water resulted in a decline in wheat yields (Abd ElAziz et al. 2022). The highest values of total plant weight of 10.116 and 12.66gm under 100 ppm and 25g FM, respectively. The lowest values were 6.84 and 6.473g, respectively without application of ZnO-NPs and 25 ppm of ZnO-NPs without FM. Additionally, wheat straw and grain had the largest relative increases, at 13.76% and

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22.73%, respectively. One explanation is that NPs have a larger surface area and are more reactive compared to conventional Zn fertilizers. This characteristic allows plants to absorb nutrients more efficiently through the small pores of their roots, thereby enhancing water and nutrient circulation within plants. As a result, this promotes overall plant growth (Ahmed et al. 2021).

In general, water use efficiency increased with optimal amount of essential nutrients both macro and micronutrients, this is due to the plants consuming low water as compared to stress conditions either stress would be abiotic or biotic (Liu et al. 2016). There was a significant interaction observed between the different levels of ZnO-NPs treatments and seed yield.

Zinc is necessary for the synthesis of natural auxin, or indole acetic acid, which in turn triggers the growth and division of cells (Elsheery et al. 2020), preservation of the character of biomembranes. Higher Zn concentrations were found to increase the germination rate and growth characteristics in maintenance seeds in ZnO-NPs (Prasad et al. 2012).

Furthermore, because of the toxicity of Na^+ ions and the decrease in osmotic potential, salinity stress hinders plant growth. Zn-NPs improve plant growth by decreasing Na^+ toxicity through decreased Na^+ absorption (Farhangi-Abriz and Torabian, 2018). Furthermore, in saline conditions, the administration of Zn-NPs generally boosted shoot fresh and dry weight (Abbasifar et al. 2020).

The decrease in chlorophyll content was attributed to damage to the chloroplasts and instability of the pigment-protein complexes (Dawood et al. 2016). ZnONPs applied to the soil at 25, 50, 75, and 100 grams per kilogram significantly enhanced the total chlorophyll levels in the leaves of wheat crops. 100 mg/L was the ZnONPs concentration that was most significant. The results resembled the results on different crop (Farnia et al., 2015) on maize (*Zea mays* L.). The application of Nano-Zn increased total chlorophyll content compared to the control (Mazaherinia et al. 2010). Key indicators used for predicting the consequences of abiotic pressures include agronomic factors including plant height, shoot length, and grain production. (Jamil et al. 2023). The lower plant height, shoot dry weight, and grain yield in the control treatment may have resulted from high salt and other soil pollutant concentrations, which also caused a reduction in photosynthetic pigments. Several studies have shown that Cd causes abiotic stress in plants, which inhibits their ability to grow (Huybrechts et al. 2019). Conversely, the application of FM and ZnO-NPs enhanced plant growth parameters, free proline levels, and photosynthetic rate, particularly when applied together.

The application of organic matter combined with ZnO-NPs, which allows plants to grow better in height, maybe may result in improved soil nutrition availability, the creation of an environment that is better for root growth through the secretion of substances that promote root growth, and the availability of nitrogen fixed by microorganisms as comparable outcomes (Bhandari et al. 2021).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The study analyzed the impact of ZnO-NPs and farm manure FM applications on wheat yield grown on saline-sodic soil. Conducted at the warehouse of the Institute of Soil and Environmental Sciences (ISES), University of Agriculture Faisalabad,

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Pakistan utilizing saline-sodic soil from Tehsil Jaranwala, Faisalabad. The experiment was a completely randomized design (CRD) with three replications, the treatments involved varying levels of ZnO-NPs and FM. Before the experiment, the soil underwent pre-analysis for various chemical parameters, including pHs, E_{Ce}, soluble Ca²⁺ + Mg²⁺, Na⁺, CO₃²⁻, HCO₃⁻, and Cl. The results demonstrated significant enhancements in several physiological parameters of wheat, such as chlorophyll content, number of tillers and number of spikes. Treatment T8 (ZnO-NP 100% + 25g FM/pot) exhibited the highest chlorophyll content, showing a 40% increase compared to the control. This study underscores the potential of ZnO-NPs and FM as effective amendments for boosting wheat productivity in salt-affected soils. It highlights the importance of sustainable agricultural practices in enhancing crop yield under challenging soil conditions.

Conclusion

In a nutshell, this study was conducted to evaluate the effects of ZnO-NPs and FM on wheat yield in saline-sodic soil. The applied treatments demonstrated significant improvements in various growth, yield and physiological attributes of wheat. Treatment T8 (ZnO-NP 100% + 25g FM) exhibited the most favorable outcomes, with notable increases in chlorophyll content, number of tillers, and number of spikes compared to the control. Additionally, treatments T1 to T8 showed consistent enhancements in these parameters, highlighting the potential of ZnO-NPs and FM as effective amendments for enhancing wheat productivity in salt-affected soils. These findings underscore the importance of sustainable agricultural practices for improving crop yield in challenging soil conditions.

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